

BREAST CANCER

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Abstract: One of the many diseases in the field of oncology—due to the fact that breast cancer is common in women and the disease increases sharply, breast cancer is more common among men in recent times, besides that, explained by the fact that it is also used in young girls. In this article, we will look at the importance of screening programs and increases the effectiveness of treatment based on the individual approach, the etio-pathogenesis of breast cancer, early diagnosis and treatment.

Key words: Oncology, etio-pathogenesis, breast cancer, diagnosis, treatment, biopsy, chemotherapy, sectoral and radical surgical treatment

SUT BEZLARI SARATONI

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Annotatsiya: Onkologiya sohasida ko'plab kuzatilayotgan kasalliklardan biri--Sut bezi saratoni ayollarda keng tarqalganligi va bu kasallik keskin ravishda ko'rsatkichlari ortib borayotganligi bilan, so'ngi paytlarda sut bezi saratoni erkaklar orasida ham ko'p uchrayotganligi bilan, shuningdek, yosh qizlarda ham kuzatilayotganligi bilan izohlanadi. Ushbu maqolada skrining dasturlarining ahamiyati va individual yondashuv asosida davolash samaradorligini oshirish, sut bezi saratonini etio-patogenezi, erta tashxislash va davolash yuzasidan ma'lumotlar ko'rib chiqiladi

Kalit so'z: Onkologiya, Sut bezi saratoni, eto-patogenezi, tashxis, davolash, biopsiya, kimyoterapiya, sektoral va radikal xirurgik davolash

Kirish: Hozirgi kunda sut bezi saratoni dunyo bo'yicha 2-o'rinni egallagan. Jahon Sog'liqni saqlash ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, yildan yilga SBS uchrash darajasi ko'paymoqda. Ushbu kasallik rivojlanishida etiologik omil, genetik omil, turmush tarzi va ekologiyaning roli katta. Bundan tashqari gormonal o'zgarishlar ham o'z tasirini o'tkazadi. Kasallikning dolzarbligi uning kech aniqlanishi va agressiv kechishi bilan bog'liq. SBS boshqa azolarga ta'siri ham kuzatiladi. Shu sababli davolashni jarrohlik, kimyoterapiya, nurlanish, gormonal va target terapiya usullarini birgalikda qo'llash orqali samarali natija olish mumkin.

Tadqiqot maqsadi:

Sut bezi saratonini erta aniqlash, aholi orasida skrining jarayonlarini kengaytirish, aholini yilda 2 marta onkolog korigidan o'tish statistikasini va tibbiy savodxonligini oshirish

Tadqiqot vazifalari:

- Sut bezi saratonining etio-patogenezini va mehanizmini o'rganish va tahlil qilish.
- SBSning kelib chiqishidagi garmonal o'zgarishlar va garmonlar tasirini o'rganish.
- Ushbu kasallikning kechishi va bosqichlarini baholash.
- SBS erta aniqlash va davolash samaradorligini oshirish

FOYALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

- 1) Siegel RL, Miller KL, Jemal A. Canser statistics, 2023
- 2) Perou CM, Sorlie T, Elsen MB, Molecular portraits of human breast tumours
- 3) Carey LA, Perou CM, Livasy CA
- 4) Kostiato